

Management

LEADERSHIP STYLE OF MIDDLE LEVEL MANAGERS IN PAKISTAN: A STUDY OF GENDER ROLE

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ABSTRACT

In this study the Transformational, Transactional and laissez faire leadership styles within the organizations are discussed. The purpose of this research was to measure the leadership style of middle level managers both males and females within organizations in Pakistan. Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire developed by Avolio and Bass in 1994 is used for this purpose. Leadership on seven factors i.e. Idealized influence, Inspirational motivation, Intellectual stimulation, Individualized Consideration, Contingent reward, Management by expectation and Laissez-faire Leadership is also measured in this research. It was concluded that overall Transactional leadership style is dominant in middle level managers of Pakistan as compare to transformational leadership style and also females are more transactional than males. Transformational leadership style is dominant in females as compared to males. Also females exhibit more Laissez Faire in contrast to males.

Keywords:

Leadership style, Transformational, Transactional, Laissez Faire, Performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Leaders always play a very important role in creating a quality culture and play a significant role in providing necessary resources for the support quality initiatives. The quality principles are necessary for developing an overall culture for organization brilliance (Blankstein 1996, Davies et al. 2007). When the leaders in the organizations show poisonous attitude toward their employees through employee monitoring and performance appraisals, the results will entirely be different from those organizations where teamwork is experienced. The leaders should adopt various measures to reduce pressure within their organizations to create a community-based organizational culture (Jacqueline et al. 2012). Best leaders always provide commitment to give more time for

coordination and instruct to create skilful manpower to achieve the organization's goals (Niazi 2008).

Leadership style in an organization is one of the factors that play considerable role in inspiring or plummeting the interest and commitment of organization's employees. Thus, Glantz (2002) felt the need for a manager to discover his leadership style. Burns (1978) describe two different words to make a distinction between "ordinary" and "extraordinary" leadership i.e. transactional and transformational leadership. Transactional leadership i.e. ordinary leadership is basically based on traditional exchange of association in which followers show effort, productivity, and loyalty just to receive the rewards (Egan et al.1995) whereas transformational (extraordinary) leaders elevate subordinates about the importance and value of results and ways how to reach destiny. Bass (1985) used the work of Burns (1978) by developing a model of transformational and transactional leadership, which is more recent study "complete leadership model" (Bass and Avolio, 1997). Bass (1985) observed that transactional leaders work in their organizations by adopting present rules and procedures, while transformational leaders change their cultures the attitude of followers by adopting new visions, values and norms. The effect of leadership style on organizational performance was investigated to determine the effect of leadership styles on performance followed by a survey design and quantitative analysis method (Obiwuru et al. 2011). Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) is best questionnaire to measure the Transformational leadership behaviors relevant to idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration and Transactional leadership behaviors relevant to contingent reward and management by exception (Alsayed et al. 2012, Hartog et al. 1997). The study concluded that transactional leadership style was more appropriate in inducing performance than transformational leadership.

In this paper Transactional, transformational and Laissez Faire leadership styles of middle level managers within the organizations in Pakistan are determined. The leadership style was measured in accordance with gender role i.e. which leadership style is dominant in males and females leaders in the organizations. As leadership style is the pattern of behaviors that leaders display during their work with and through others (Hersey and Blanchard, 1993). So it is necessary to determine how they work and how males and females as leaders bring positive changes in their organization.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire is used developed by Bass and Avolio, 1994. Instrument is widely known as MLQ. There are 21 questions and each research statement has five possible answers ranging from "not at all" to "frequently, if not always" and is scaled from 1 to 5. MLQ v6 examine the leadership behavior on seven dimensions.

The copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents with instructions on how to fill them out. 100 questionnaires were distributed among 50 males and 50 females out of which 70 were received and 50 were found usable for this research

- Sample Size** = 50
- Female Respondents = 25
- Male Respondents = 25

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research cluster Sampling was used as sampling method. It is different from other statistical measures because it has advantage to cluster cases or individuals together based on a whole set of scores or variables (Filsinger, 1990). By providing the nature of the independent variable, with each gender having a score for each of the various dimensions of leadership, cluster analysis was a useful tool in the analysis of the data for this study, especially given that males and females were assessed individually with many scores making up various combinations of leadership styles.

CENTRAL QUESTIONS OF RESEARCH

Does there any difference between leadership styles of genders?
What style of leadership is needed to motivate people to undertake change?

RELIABILITY TEST

The reliability of the factors effecting leadership style was determined by using Cronbach’s alpha method. Cronbach’s alpha measures the average of measurable items and its correlation, and if the result is generally above 0.5 (or 50%); it is considered to be reliable (Peighambari, 2007).

Table1: (Reliability of Leadership)

Dimensions	Reliability
Idealized influence	0.663
Inspirational motivation	0.677
Intellectual stimulation	0.577
Individualized consideration	0.624
Contingent reward	0.647
Management by exception	0.543
Laissez faire	0.676

METHOD APPROACH

The data analysis was done by using cross tab analysis with the help of SPSS while initiating preliminary findings (Hasan et al. 2006).

Figure 1: Cross Tab Analysis: Idealized influence

Idealized influence is dominant in males as compared to females, indicating these leaders help their subordinates to develop trust, maintain their loyalty and esteem, and show dedication to them and act as their role model (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Cross Tab Analysis: Inspirational motivation

Inspirational motivation is dominant in females as compared to males (Figure 2) indicating that such type of leaders provide a vision, help their employees to focus on their work and try to make others feel their work is of some worth.

Figure 3: Cross Tab Analysis: Intellectual stimulation

Intellectual stimulation is dominant in females as compared to males (Figure 3) indicating the extent to which these leaders encourage subordinates to look at old problems in new ways. They create an environment that is understanding and cultivate people to realize their own values and beliefs and also those of the organization.

Figure 4: Cross Tab Analysis: Individual consideration

Individual consideration is dominant in females as compared to males, indicating the level to which these leaders show interest in others well-being and pay attention to those who appear to be less involved in the group (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Cross Tab Analysis: Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership style is high in females as compare to males in middle level management of Pakistan (Figure 5).

Figure 6: Cross Tab Analysis: Contingent reward

Contingent reward is dominant in females as compared to males (Figure 6) indicating the extent to which these managers tell others what to do in order to get reward. They just show ordinary behavior.

Figure 7: Cross Tab Analysis: Management by exception

The figure (7) shows that Management by exception is dominant in males as compared to females, indicating the degree to which they assess whether they tell others the job requirements pertinent to standard performance.

Figure 8: Cross Tab Analysis: Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership style in case of male is moderate while in females it may be high and low as contingent reward is high in females and management by exception is high in case of males (Figure 8).

Figure 9: Cross Tab Analysis: Laissez-faire leadership

Laissez Faire leadership style is dominant in females as compared to males (Figure 9) which measures whether they require little of others, have low decision making and avoid responsibility. These leaders leave group members alone and only interact when there are certain challenges. It was observed from above study that Transactional leadership style is most often used leadership style; transformational leadership is less frequently used and laissez-faire was noted as the least commonly used leadership style.

4. CONCLUSION

It is necessary to pay more attention in developing leaders' management skills and knowledge. Following results were obtained from the present study:

- Reliability of Cronbach Alpha co-efficient indicates that the scale for this research is reliable.
- Overall Transactional leadership style is dominant as compare to transformational leadership style in both male and female community
- Transformational leadership style is high in females as compare to males in middle level management
- Laissez-Faire leadership style is dominant in females as compared to males
- Males in Pakistan show moderate behavior as a leader in the organizations
- However, Idealized influence and Management by exception is high in males as compared to females

5. FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

As Leadership is the process of influencing and supporting others to work passionately toward achieving goals and combine technical, human, and conceptual skills, which he/she applies at different organizational levels. For the purpose of bringing effective changes in leadership style of middle level managers of Pakistan there are certain future implications which are given below:

- Training and development is needed to shape leadership style
- In case of females, Laissez-Faire Leadership is controlled by education and training
- In case of males it is needed to boost up leadership behavior by proper training
- At the time of hiring it must be noted that which leadership style is needed in organizations

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Alsayed, A. K., Motaghi, M. H., Osman, I. B. (2012). *The Use of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire and Communication Satisfaction Questionnaire in Palestine: A Research Note. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2: 1-9.
- [2] Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and Performance beyond Expectations*. New York, Free Press.
- [3] Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1994). *Improving organizational Effectiveness through Transformational Leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [4] Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. (1997). *Full Range Leadership Development: Manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire*. Palo Alto, CA: Mind Garden.
- [5] Blankstein, A. M. (1996). *Why TQM can't work – and a school where it did. Education Digest*, 62: 27-30.
- [6] Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership*. New York: Harper & Row.
- [7] Davies, J., Douglas, A., & Douglas, J. (2007). *The effect of academic culture on the implementation of the EFQM Excellence Model in UK universities. Quality Assurance in Education*, 15: 382-401.

- [8] Egan R. F. C., Sarros J. C., & Santaro J. C. (1995). *Putting transactional and transformational leadership into practice. Journal of Leadership Studies*, 2: 100-123.
- [9] Filsinger, E. E. (1990). *Empirical typology, cluster analysis, and family-level measurement. In T. W. Draper & A. C. Marcos (Eds.), Family variables: Conceptualization, measurement, and use (pp. 90-104). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.*
- [10] Glantz, J. (2002). *Finding Your Leadership Style. A Guide for Educators; Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.*
- [11] Hartog, D. N. D. Van Muijen, J. J. & Koopman P. L. (1997). *Transactional versus transformational leadership: An analysis of the MLQ, Journal of occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 70: 19-34.
- [12] Hasan A. A., & Khoury, G. C. (2006). *Leadership styles in the Palestinian large-scale industrial enterprises, Journal of Management Development*, 25: 832 – 849.
- [13] Hersey, P., & Blanchard, K. (1993). *Management of organizational behavior: Utilizing humanresources, 6th ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, Inc.*
- [14] Jacqueline A. Gilbert, Norma Carr-Ruffino, John M. Ivancevich, Robert Konopaske (2012). *Toxic versus cooperative behaviors at work: the role of organizational culture and leadership in creating community-centered organizations, International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 7: 29-47.
- [15] Niazi I. (2008). *A Comparative Study of Quality of Education in Public and Private Secondary Schools of Punjab. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University Institute of Education and Research. Pir Mehr Ali Shah, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, 47.*
- [16] Obiwuru, T. C., Okwu, A. T., Apka, V. O., Nwankwere, I. A. (2011). *Effects of leadership style on organizational performance: A survey of selected small scale enterprises in IKOSI-KETU Council Development are of Lagos State, Nigeria, Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1:100-111.
- [17] Peighambari, K. (2007). *Developing and Testing a Model for Explaining Customer Retention Formation. Master Thesis, Tarbiat Modares University. Retrieved from <http://luth.se/1653-0182/2007/066/LTU-PB-EX-07066-SE.Pdf>.*